

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Liquid Phase Exfoliation of Arsenic Trisulfide (As_2S_3) Nanosheets and Their Use as Anodes in Potassium Ion Batteries

Harneet Kaur¹, Bharathi Konkena^{1,§}, Mark McCrystall^{1,§}, Kevin Synnatschke¹, Cian Gabbett¹, Jose Munuera¹, Ross Smith¹, Yumei Jiang¹, Raman Bekarevich², Lewys Jones¹, Valeria Nicolosi², & Jonathan N Coleman^{1}*

¹School of Physics, CRANN & AMBER Research Centres, Trinity College Dublin, Dublin 2, D02 E8C0, Ireland

²School of Chemistry, CRANN & AMBER Research Centres, Trinity College Dublin, Dublin 2, D02W9K7, Ireland

*colemaj@tcd.ie (Jonathan N. Coleman); Tel: +353 (0) 1 8963859.

§authors contributed equally to this work

CONTENTS:

	Page no.
A: SAED, TEM-EDX and step-height analysis of exfoliated nanosheets of As_2S_3 .	2-3
B: Free-standing As_2S_3 @CNT electrode, post-mortem analysis of SEM-EDX, X-ray diffraction pattern and voltage profiles.	3-6
C: Literature comparison of this work with others.	6-11
References	12-15

A. SAED pattern, EDX and Step-height analysis of exfoliated nanosheets of As_2S_3 .

a. Selected area-electron diffraction (SAED) pattern from a few-layer thick As_2S_3 nanosheet.

The selected area diffraction pattern (SAED) obtained from a few-layered thick nanosheet provides valuable insights into the crystallography and structural characteristics of the material. It reveals the nanosheet of As_2S_3 is oriented in the $[010]$ direction and show the periodicity of the crystal lattice (Crystal System: Monoclinic, SPGR: $P21/n$).

Figure S1: (A) SAED from an As_2S_3 nanosheet. (B) Assignment of the diffraction spot pattern to the monoclinic crystal system, and space group $P21/n$.

b. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) of As_2S_3 nanosheets for stoichiometry

Figure S2. TEM-EDX analysis on 24 randomly selected 2D-nanoplatelets. The $\langle \text{S/As} \rangle$ ratio is in line with expectations and is plotted as a histogram.

Exfoliated As₂S₃ nanosheets were analyzed using EDX spectra, and the results are shown in Figure S2. The analysis confirmed the existence of As and S elements with an average atomic ratio of $\langle S/As \rangle : 1.5$

c. Step-height analysis of exfoliated nanosheet.

In this context, step-height analysis pertains to the precise measurement and evaluation of the nanosheet's thickness at the atomic scale. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) is employed to accurately determine the thickness of these nanosheets. Within the AFM images, nanosheets are identified at locations exhibiting distinct steps or edges, exemplified in Figure S3. A line profile is generated across these steps using AFM software Gwyddion, and the height difference referred to as step height, is recorded. To enhance the accuracy of our analysis, measurements are conducted at multiple positions on various nanosheets, and statistical analysis was performed to find the minimum step-height. Subsequently, the actual thickness (t_{real}) of the nanosheets is derived based on these measurements, utilizing the following formula:

$$t_{real} = \frac{t_{apparent}}{\text{Minimum step height}} \times t_{monolayer}$$

The values for $t_{apparent}$ are compiled from the AFM height measurements conducted on over 100 nanosheets, while the minimum step height is determined to be 2 nm. Notably, the monolayer thickness is calculated as half of the unit cell thickness along the b-axis, which is determined to be 0.48 nm. This rigorous approach ensures accurate assessment of the nanosheet thickness.

Figure S3: AFM image of an As_2S_3 nanosheet with clear steps. A line profile (black line) generated across the nanosheet display clear steps as shown, and the step height analysis over various nanosheets shows a minimum step height of 2 nm.

B: Free-standing, electrochemical performance of SWCNTs electrode, post cycling analysis of As_2S_3 @CNT electrodes and Voltage profiles.

a. Free standing As_2S_3 @CNT electrode

The electrode is composed of 70% by weight of As_2S_3 nanosheets and 30% by weight of SWCNT. The mass loading of the electrode is measured at 0.44 mg/cm^2 . To prepare the electrode materials, the dispersions of As_2S_3 and SWCNT in solvent 2-propanol were mixed at the required weight ratio (7:3) to create the final dispersion containing 1D SWCNT and 2D- As_2S_3 nanosheets. This mixture is then bath sonicated for 30 minutes at room temperature to ensure uniform mixing, followed by filtering the final dispersion onto a Celgard membrane. Once the entire solution was filtered, the film on the membrane was allowed to dry under a vacuum pump, and subsequently stored in a glove box overnight. The resulting dried film was easily peeled off from the membrane, yielding a free standing As_2S_3 @CNT electrode, as depicted in Figure S4.

Figure S4: (A) The photograph of a free-standing $\text{As}_2\text{S}_3@\text{CNT}$ electrode. The electrode is held with forceps and rotated to capture the top, side, and bottom views of the electrode. (B) SEM cross-section image of the composite film with the corresponding elemental composition maps, for (C) As; (D) S. (E) EDX spectra of the composite electrode, indicate the presence of As and S elements in the composite electrode. Elemental maps reveal a uniform distribution of As and S elements with an expected stoichiometry of $\text{As}_2\text{S}_{3.1}$.

b. Specific capacity of SWCNTs alone K-ion battery anode

To determine the capacity contribution of CNTs, we conducted a cycling test on SWCNTs electrodes alone at 50 mA/g for 10 cycles and 200 mA/g for 40 cycles, as shown in Figure S5. The results indicate that the specific capacity of SWCNTs for K-ion storage is approximately 32 mAh/g at 200 mA/g. As we used 30 wt% SWNTs, the maximum contribution of SWCNTs in our electrodes is 9.6 mAh/g, which is relatively small compared to the overall electrode capacity of over 450 mAh/g.

Figure S5: Cycling performance of SWCNTs film alone for K-ion storage at a current density of 50 and 200 mA/g.

c. Voltage profiles

Figure S6: (A) Voltage profiles for the initial five galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) cycles. (B) Voltage profiles during the extended activation cycles at 50th, 100th, 124th, 155th, 180th and 200th cycles, at a current density of 200 mA/g. (C) Voltage profiles collected at different current densities and its differential voltage profiles (D). At low current density, the sharp peaks at 0.09 V and 0.36 V, indicating that highly reversible alloy and de-alloying reactions. With increasing current density, the voltage hysteresis between alloy and de-alloy reaction peaks is increasing, leading to poor charge storage at high current densities.

d. Post-mortem SEM and Ex-situ X-ray diffraction analysis of $\text{As}_2\text{S}_3@\text{CNT}$ electrode after 200 GCD cycles.

The cell was first subjected to a ten-step process of cyclic voltammetry to establish the solid electrolyte interphase formation, followed by galvanostatic cycling at a current density of 200 mA/g for a total of 200 cycles. After this, the cell was de-potassiated to 2 V, opened and the electrode was carefully extracted for SEM and XRD measurements. The SEM image in Figure

S7 demonstrates that the electrode surface appears smoother, with no apparent 2D-platelets, indicating a consistent and non-crystalline structure. It is evident that conversion-type materials experience a change in shape during cycling, making it highly improbable for them to maintain their original morphology after cycling. After 200 cycles, the SEM-EDX elemental maps were used to analyze the distribution of As and S elements in the cross-sectional film of the $\text{As}_2\text{S}_3/\text{CNT}$ composite electrode to demonstrate its structural stability (Figure S8). After cycling, the electrodes exhibited the distribution of As and S elements, as well as the distribution of K, P, and F from the electrolyte.

The XRD pattern of the activated electrode (Figure S7) exhibited a broad peak within the 2-theta range of $10\text{-}21^\circ$, which is characteristic of amorphous As_2S_3 .^{1, 2} Additionally, a more distinct peak at approximately 22° corresponded to the (002) reflection of SWCNT. The presence of XRD peaks from the copper foil is due to the electrode adhering to the foil.

Figure S7: SEM image and X-ray diffraction pattern of the electrode after 200 charge/discharge cycles.

Figure S8. (A) SEM cross-section image of $\text{As}_2\text{S}_3/\text{CNT}$ composite electrode after 200 charge-discharge cycles. The elemental mapping on the post-cycled electrode surface, for (B) S; (C) As; (D) P (E) K and (F) fluorine from the electrolyte. (G) O on the electrode surface (from SEI and oxidation after washing the electrodes). (G) EDX spectra on the post-cycled electrode represent the presence of As and S elements. Elemental maps of the electrode revealed a uniform distribution of As, S, K, P, and F elements.

C. Literature comparison of this work with others.

a. Literature comparison of As_2S_3 (this work) with other 2D materials based KIB anodes

Table S1. The literature comparison on the specific capacities, and capacity retention other 2D materials based KIB anodes of this work with other state-of-the-art latest 2D materials based KIB anodes (except for carbon/graphite).

Anode	Highest stable specific capacity (mAh/g) @ Current density (mA/g)	Number of cycles	Current density (mA/g) of cycling	Capacity at the end of cycling (mAh/g)	Capacity retention (%)	Reference
$\text{As}_2\text{S}_3@\text{CNT}$	619@50 550@100	1000	500	237	94	This work
$\text{FePSe}_3@\text{CNT}$	472@50	500	500	223	74	³
$\text{CoVMnFeZnPS}_3@\text{graphite}$	500@50	1000	500	340	85	⁴
$\text{Nb}_2\text{C}@\text{rGO}$	352@100	1000	10000	199	83.3	⁵

Co-SLMoS ₂ @NOC	610@100	1000 3000	5000 5000	350 325	82 79	6
Ti ₃ C ₂ @C	288@100	1000	500	174	87	7
MoS ₂ -C@rGO	405@100	2000	2000	161	70	8
MnPSe ₃ @graphite	341@50	700	250	236	91.5	9
WS ₂ @SPAN	362@100	3000	1000	-	-	10
CNS@Ti ₃ C ₂	306@100	1000	500	205	95	11
MXene@Bi ₂ S ₃ -Mo ₇ S ₈	581@200	1000	380	276	67.1	12
Co ₃ C-MXene@C	323@100	500	500	129	67	13
SnTe@rGO@NC	243.9@50	50	1000	112	89.4	14
Sb@MoS ₂ @NC	390@50	80	50	210	52	15
FeS ₂ @C-rGO	526@100	500	2000	171	57	16
Bi _{0.51} Sb _{0.49} OCl@rGO	407@100	1000	100	360	88.4	17
MoS ₂ on NC	498@200	5000	1000	399	95	18
MoSe ₂ on NC	393@200	4800	1000	247	85	18
MoS ₂ @C	203@50	1500	500	114	80	19
Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x @NCRib	371@100	1000	1000	201.5	-	20
Sb ₂ S ₃ @C	500@50	200	500	400	-	21
WSe ₂ @C	393@50	500	1000	209	94.4	22
Nb ₂ C@C	398@20	200	100	257	76.2	23
MoS _{1.5} Se _{0.5} @NC	860@50	400	5000	276	80	24
MoS ₂ @MXene	290@50	100	50	206	75.9	25
MoSe ₂ @NCT	300@100	100	200	230	-	26
N-doped Graphene	350@50	100	100	210	78	27
SnS ₂ @MXene	342@50	800	500	206	-	28
Ta ₂ NiSe ₅	308@50	1100	500	116	81.4	29
ZnS QD-rGO	340@50	500	1000	122	92	30
Sb@Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	500@100	1000	1000	314	94	31
BP@V ₂ CT _x	593@100	3000	2000	261	-	32
CuSbS ₂	550@100	-	-	-	-	33
Bi ₂ Se ₃ @C	526@50	1000	1000	214	-	34
CoSe ₂ @NC/MXene	430@100	200	500	180	60	35
1T-MoS ₂ @V ₂ CF ₂	874@100	500	100	664	83.5	36
VS ₂ @C	488@100	50	100	436	89.3	37

b. Rate performance and cycling comparison of As_2S_3 (this work) with reported Sb_2S_3 , and Bi_2S_3 based KIB anodes.

Table S2. A comparative analysis of the rate and cycling performance of As_2S_3 (this work) in comparison with Sb_2S_3 and Bi_2S_3 -based KIB anodes in published studies.

Morphology of Sb_2S_3 or Bi_2S_3 in the active material	Active material	Rate performance (C_{specific} @current density (mA/g))	Number of cycles	Current density (mA/g)	C_{specific} at the end of cycling	Capacity retention (%)	Reference
Nanosheet	As_2S_3	619@50 550@100 459@200 257@500 171@1000 109@2000	1000	500	237	94	This work
Core shell nanofiber	Sb_2S_3 - C@ Nb_2O_5 -C	350@100 300@200 275@500 200@1000 148@2000	2200	2000	96	64	³⁸
Nanoflower	Sb_2S_3 @ Ti_3C_2	357@100 297@200 229@500 168@1000 102@2000	500	100	286	80	³⁹
Nanotube	Sb/ Sb_2S_3 @Carbon hollow tube	608@50 556@100 446@200 349@500 263@1000 173@2000	3500	1000	200	76	⁴⁰
Nanorod	Sb_2S_3 @r GO@N C	513@50 353@100 253@200 147@500 76@1000	200	200	89	35	⁴¹
Microrods	Sb_2S_3 - Bi_2S_3 @ C@rGO	558@100 503@200 446@300 395@400 319@500 182@1000	80	200	300	60	⁴²

Nanoparticle	Sb ₂ S ₃ @MXene	434@50 372@100 326@200 294@500 207@1000 119@2000	100	50	422	97	⁴³
Nanosphere	Sb ₂ S ₃ @CNT	446@50 254@100 222@500 166@1000	50	500	212	95	⁴⁴
Yolk-shell	Sb ₂ S ₃ @NSC	629@50 579@100 547@200 495@500 423@1000 313@2000 210@4000	2000	1000	248	59	⁴⁵
Nanocrystals	CoS ₂ /Sb ₂ S ₃ @NC/CNT	538@100 389@200 319@500 264@1000 226@2000 133@5000	50	200	453	-	⁴⁶
Nanoparticle	Sb ₂ S ₃ @S, N-doped graphene	547@20 535@50 500@100 460@200 420@500 340@1000	100	50	500	94	⁴⁷
Nanosheet	Sb ₂ S ₃ @C	500@50 450@100 400@200 250@300 175@500 100@1000	50	50	350	70	²¹
Nanorod	Bi ₂ S ₃ @rGO	579@100 562@300 541@600 292@1000 162@3000	1000	100	410	71	⁴⁸
Nanospheres	Se-doped Bi ₂ S ₃ @ReS ₂	450@100 400@200 350@500 300@1000 100@2000 50@3000	900	1000	200	67	⁴⁹

Core-shell	Bi ₂ S ₃ @S -doped C	450@50 430@100 400@200 354@400 328@600 297@800 268@1000	250	500	160	46	⁵⁰
Nanocluster	Bi ₂ S ₃ /M oS ₂ @N- dopedC	550@100 516@200 484@500 458@1000 424@2000 381@5000	400	500	412	85	⁵¹
Nanowire	Bi ₂ S ₃ /Bi ₂ Se ₃	604@50 477@100 372@250 302@500 255@1000 221@1500 196@2000 89@3500	1000	500	200	66	⁵²
Microsphere	Bi ₂ S ₃ @r GO	370@50 328@80 320@100 260@300	1200	100	206	64	⁵³
Microsphere	Bi ₂ S ₃ @r GO	550@200 450@500 400@1000 300@1500 250@2000	300	2000	237	95	⁵⁴
Nanorod	Bi ₂ S ₃ @r GO	231@100 158@200 109@500 75@1000	150	200	100.8	63	⁵⁵
Nanorod	Bi ₂ S ₃ @i odine- doped graphen e	453@50 373@100 304@200 241@500 169@1000 78@2000	200	100	300	81	⁵⁶

References:

1. De Neufville, J. P.; Moss, S. C.; Ovshinsky, S. R., Photostructural Transformations in Amorphous As₂Se₃ and As₂S₃ Films. *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **1974**, *13* (2), 191-223 %@ 0022-3093.
2. Shpotyuk, O.; Demchenko, P.; Shpotyuk, Y.; Bujňáková, Z.; Baláž, P., Medium-Range Structural Changes in Glassy As₂S₃ Driven by High-Energy Mechanical Milling. *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **2019**, *505*, 347-353 %@ 0022-3093.
3. Huang, Y.-F.; Yang, Y.-C.; Tuan, H.-Y., Construction of Strongly Coupled Few-Layer FePSe₃-Cnt Hybrids for High Performance Potassium-Ion Storage Devices. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2023**, *451*, 139013 %@ 1385-8947.
4. Chien, P.-W.; Chang, C.-B.; Tuan, H.-Y., High-Entropy Two-Dimensional Metal Phosphorus Trichalcogenides Boost High-Performance Potassium Ion Storage Devices Via Electrochemical Reconstruction. *Energy Storage Materials* **2023**, 102853 %@ 2405-8297.
5. Liu, C.; Fang, Z.; Li, X.; Zhou, J.; Yang, G.; Peng, L.; Guo, X.; Ding, W.; Hou, W., Rational Design of 3d Porous Niobium Carbide Mxene/Rgo Hybrid Aerogels as Promising Anode for Potassium-Ion Batteries with Ultrahigh Rate Capability. *Nano Research* **2023**, *16* (2), 2463-2473 %@ 1998-0124.
6. Li, Z.; Han, M.; Zhang, Y.; Yuan, F.; Fu, Y.; Yu, J., Single-Layered Mos₂ Fabricated by Charge-Driven Interlayer Expansion for Superior Lithium/Sodium/Potassium-Ion-Battery Anodes. *Advanced Science* **2023**, *10* (15), 2207234 %@ 2198-3844.
7. Wu, S.; Feng, Y.; Wu, K.; Jiang, W.; Xue, Z.; Xiong, D.; Chen, L.; Feng, Z.; Wen, K.; Li, Z., Mxene Ti₃C₂ Generated TiO₂ Nanoparticles in Situ and Uniformly Embedded in Rgo Sheets as High Stable Anodes for Potassium Ion Batteries. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* **2023**, *930*, 167414 %@ 0925-8388.
8. Li, J.; Hu, F.; Wei, H.; Hei, J.; Yin, Y.; Liu, G.; Wang, N.; Wei, H., Confining Mos₂/C Nanoparticles on Two-Dimensional Graphene Sheets for High Reversible Capacity and Long-Life Potassium Ions Batteries. *Composites Part B: Engineering* **2023**, *250*, 110424 %@ 1359-8368.
9. Huang, Y.-F.; Yang, Y.-C.; Tseng, Y.-Y.; Tuan, H.-Y., Two Dimensional Mnpse₃ Layer Stacking Composites with Superior Storage Performance for Alkali Metal-Ion Batteries. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2023**, *635*, 336-347 %@ 0021-9797.
10. Lei, Z.; Zheng, J.; He, X.; Wang, Y.; Yang, X.; Xiao, F.; Xue, H.; Xiong, P.; Wei, M.; Chen, Q., Defect-Rich Ws₂-Span Nanofibers for Sodium/Potassium-Ion Batteries: Ultralong Lifespans and Wide-Temperature Workability. *Inorganic Chemistry Frontiers* **2023**, *10* (4), 1187-1196.
11. Feng, Y.; Wu, K.; Wu, S.; Guo, Y.; He, M.; Xue, M., Carbon Quantum Dots-Derived Carbon Nanosphere Coating on Ti₃C₂ Mxene as a Superior Anode for High-Performance Potassium-Ion Batteries. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2023**, *15* (2), 3077-3088 %@ 1944-8244.
12. Wang, M.; Qin, B.; Xu, F.; Yang, W.; Liu, Z.; Zhang, Y.; Fan, H., Hetero-Structural and Hetero-Interfacial Engineering of Mxene@ Bi₂S₃/Mo₇S₈ Hybrid for Advanced Sodium/Potassium-Ion Batteries. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2023**, *650*, 446-455 %@ 0021-9797.
13. Zhang, H.; Xiong, D.; Xie, Y.; Wu, K.; Feng, Z.; Wen, K.; Li, Z.; He, M., Co₃C/Mxene Composites Wrapped in N-Rich Carbon as Stable-Performance Anodes for Potassium/Sodium-Ion Batteries. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **2023**, *656*, 130332 %@ 0927-7757.
14. Li, T.; Wang, Y.; Zhou, Q.; Yuan, L.; Qiao, S.; Ma, M.; Liu, Z.; Chong, S., Snte Nanoparticles Physicochemically Encapsulated by Double Carbon as Conversion-Alloying Anode Materials for Superior Potassium-Ion Batteries. *Journal of Materials Science & Technology* **2023**, *158*, 86-95 %@ 1005-0302.
15. Suo, G.; Zhang, J.; Li, R.; Ma, Z.; Cheng, Y.; Ahmed, S. M., Antimony Anchored in Mos₂ Nanosheets with N-Doped Carbon Coating to Boost Potassium Storage Performance. *Materials Today Chemistry* **2023**, *27*, 101300 %@ 2468-5194.

16. Zhou, X.; Wang, Z.; Wang, Y.; Du, F.; Li, Y.; Su, Y.; Wang, M.; Ma, M.; Yang, G.; Ding, S., Graphene Supported Fes₂ Nanoparticles with Sandwich Structure as a Promising Anode for High-Rate Potassium-Ion Batteries. *Journal of colloid and interface science* **2023**, *636*, 73-82 %@ 0021-9797.
17. Wang, J.; Wang, B.; Lu, B., Nature of Novel 2d Van Der Waals Heterostructures for Superior Potassium Ion Batteries. *Advanced Energy Materials* **2020**, *10* (24), 2000884 %@ 1614-6832.
18. Ma, M.; Zhang, S.; Yao, Y.; Wang, H.; Huang, H.; Xu, R.; Wang, J.; Zhou, X.; Yang, W.; Peng, Z., Heterostructures of 2d Molybdenum Dichalcogenide on 2d Nitrogen-Doped Carbon: Superior Potassium-Ion Storage and Insight into Potassium Storage Mechanism. *Advanced Materials* **2020**, *32* (22), 2000958 %@ 0935-9648.
19. Wang, H.; Niu, J.; Shi, J.; Lv, W.; Wang, H.; van Aken, P. A.; Zhang, Z.; Chen, R.; Huang, W., Facile Preparation of Mos₂ Nanocomposites for Efficient Potassium-Ion Batteries by Grinding-Promoted Intercalation Exfoliation. *Small* **2021**, *17* (34), 2102263 %@ 1613-6810.
20. Cao, J.; Sun, Z.; Li, J.; Zhu, Y.; Yuan, Z.; Zhang, Y.; Li, D.; Wang, L.; Han, W., Microbe-Assisted Assembly of Ti₃C₂T_x Mxene on Fungi-Derived Nanoribbon Heterostructures for Ultrastable Sodium and Potassium Ion Storage. *ACS nano* **2021**, *15* (2), 3423-3433 %@ 1936-0851.
21. Liu, Y.; Tai, Z.; Zhang, J.; Pang, W. K.; Zhang, Q.; Feng, H.; Konstantinov, K.; Guo, Z.; Liu, H. K., Boosting Potassium-Ion Batteries by Few-Layered Composite Anodes Prepared Via Solution-Triggered One-Step Shear Exfoliation. *Nature communications* **2018**, *9* (1), 3645 %@ 2041-1723.
22. Xing, L.; Han, K.; Liu, Q.; Liu, Z.; Chu, J.; Zhang, L.; Ma, X.; Bao, Y.; Li, P.; Wang, W., Hierarchical Two-Atom-Layered Wse₂/C Ultrathin Crumpled Nanosheets Assemblies: Engineering the Interlayer Spacing Boosts Potassium-Ion Storage. *Energy Storage Mater.* **2021**, *36*, 309–317 (2021). 2021.
23. Liu, C.; Zhou, J.; Li, X.; Fang, Z.; Sun, R.; Yang, G.; Hou, W., Surface Modification and in Situ Carbon Intercalation of Two-Dimensional Niobium Carbide as Promising Electrode Materials for Potassium-Ion Batteries. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2022**, *431*, 133838 %@ 1385-8947.
24. Fan, H. N.; Wang, X. Y.; Yu, H. B.; Gu, Q. F.; Chen, S. L.; Liu, Z.; Chen, X. H.; Luo, W. B.; Liu, H. K., Enhanced Potassium Ion Battery by Inducing Interlayer Anionic Ligands in Mos_{1.5}Se_{0.5} Nanosheets with Exploration of the Mechanism. *Advanced Energy Materials* **2020**, *10* (21), 1904162 %@ 1614-6832.
25. Li, J.; Rui, B.; Wei, W.; Nie, P.; Chang, L.; Le, Z.; Liu, M.; Wang, H.; Wang, L.; Zhang, X., Nanosheets Assembled Layered Mos₂/Mxene as High Performance Anode Materials for Potassium Ion Batteries. *Journal of Power Sources* **2020**, *449*, 227481 %@ 0378-7753.
26. Li, N.; Sun, L.; Wang, K.; Zhang, J.; Liu, X., Anchoring Mose₂ Nanosheets on N-Doped Carbon Nanotubes as High Performance Anodes for Potassium-Ion Batteries. *Electrochimica Acta* **2020**, *360*, 136983 %@ 0013-4686.
27. Share, K.; Cohn, A. P.; Carter, R.; Rogers, B.; Pint, C. L., Role of Nitrogen-Doped Graphene for Improved High-Capacity Potassium Ion Battery Anodes. *ACS nano* **2016**, *10* (10), 9738-9744 %@ 1936-0851.
28. Cao, Y.; Chen, H.; Shen, Y.; Chen, M.; Zhang, Y.; Zhang, L.; Wang, Q.; Guo, S.; Yang, H., Sns₂ Nanosheets Anchored on Nitrogen and Sulfur Co-Doped Mxene Sheets for High-Performance Potassium-Ion Batteries. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2021**, *13* (15), 17668-17676 %@ 1944-8244.
29. Tian, H.; Yu, X.; Shao, H.; Dong, L.; Chen, Y.; Fang, X.; Wang, C.; Han, W.; Wang, G., Unlocking Few-Layered Ternary Chalcogenides for High-Performance Potassium-Ion Storage. *Advanced Energy Materials* **2019**, *9* (29), 1901560 %@ 1614-6832.
30. Qi, Y.; Yang, Y.; Hou, Q.; Zhang, K.; Zhao, H.; Su, H.; Zhou, L.; Liu, X.; Shen, C.; Xie, K., Uniform-Dispersed Zns Quantum Dots Loading on Graphene as a Promising Anode for Potassium-Ion Batteries. *Chinese Chemical Letters* **2021**, *32* (3), 1117-1120 %@ 1001-8417.
31. Guo, X.; Gao, H.; Wang, S.; Yang, G.; Zhang, X.; Zhang, J.; Liu, H.; Wang, G., Mxene-Based Aerogel Anchored with Antimony Single Atoms and Quantum Dots for High-Performance Potassium-Ion Batteries. *Nano Letters* **2022**, *22* (3), 1225-1232 %@ 1530-6984.

32. Wu, X.; Wang, H.; Zhao, Z.; Huang, B., Interstratification-Assembled 2d Black Phosphorene and V₂Ct X Mxene as Superior Anodes for Boosting Potassium-Ion Storage. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* **2020**, *8* (25), 12705-12715.
33. Chang, C.-B.; Chen, K.-T.; Tuan, H.-Y., Large-Scale Synthesis of Few-Layered Copper Antimony Sulfide Nanosheets as Electrode Materials for High-Rate Potassium-Ion Storage. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2022**, *608*, 984-994 %@ 0021-9797.
34. Zhao, X.; Zhang, C.; Yang, G.; Wu, Y.; Fu, Q.; Zhao, H.; Lei, Y., Bismuth Selenide Nanosheets Confined in Thin Carbon Layers as Anode Materials for Advanced Potassium-Ion Batteries. *Inorganic Chemistry Frontiers* **2021**, *8* (18), 4267-4275.
35. Oh, H. G.; Yang, S. H.; Kang, Y. C.; Park, S. K., N-Doped Carbon-Coated CoSe₂ Nanocrystals Anchored on Two-Dimensional Mxene Nanosheets for Efficient Electrochemical Sodium-and Potassium-Ion Storage. *International Journal of Energy Research* **2021**, *45* (12), 17738-17748 %@ 0363-907X.
36. Wang, H.; Jia, B.; Zhao, Z.; Luo, C.; Wu, X., Interlayer Spacing Enlarged 2d 1t-MoS₂ and V₂CtX Mxene as Superior Anodes for Boosting Potassium-Ion Diffusion Coefficient. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2022**, *618*, 56-67 %@ 0021-9797.
37. Xie, X.-C.; Shuai, H.-L.; Wu, X.; Huang, K.-J.; Wang, L.-N.; Wang, R.-M.; Chen, Y., Engineering Ultra-Enlarged Interlayer Carbon-Containing Vanadium Disulfide Composite for High-Performance Sodium and Potassium Ion Storage. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* **2020**, *847*, 156288 %@ 0925-8388.
38. Liu, H.; He, Y.; Cao, K.; Wang, S.; Jiang, Y.; Liu, X.; Huang, K. J.; Jing, Q. S.; Jiao, L., Stimulating the Reversibility of Sb₂S₃ Anode for High-Performance Potassium-Ion Batteries. *Small* **2021**, *17* (10), 2008133 %@ 1613-6810.
39. Wang, T.; Shen, D.; Liu, H.; Chen, H.; Liu, Q.; Lu, B., A Sb₂S₃ Nanoflower/Mxene Composite as an Anode for Potassium-Ion Batteries. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2020**, *12* (52), 57907-57915 %@ 1944-8244.
40. Wu, Y.; Zheng, J.; Tong, Y.; Liu, X.; Sun, Y.; Niu, L.; Li, H., Carbon Hollow Tube-Confined Sb/Sb₂S₃ Nanorod Fragments as Highly Stable Anodes for Potassium-Ion Batteries. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2021**, *13* (43), 51066-51077 %@ 1944-8244.
41. Chong, S.; Qiao, S.; Wei, X.; Li, T.; Yuan, L.; Dong, S.; Huang, W., Sb₂S₃-Based Conversion-Alloying Dual Mechanism Anode for Potassium-Ion Batteries. *Iscience* **2021**, *24* (12 %@ 2589-0042).
42. Li, K.; Liu, X.; Qin, Y.; Zhao, Z.; Xu, Y.; Yi, Y.; Guan, H.; Fu, Y.; Liu, P.; Li, D., Sb₂S₃-Bi₂S₃ Microrods with the Combined Action of Carbon Encapsulation and Rgo Confinement for Improving High Cycle Stability in Sodium/Potassium Storage. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2021**, *414*, 128787 %@ 1385-8947.
43. Zhang, P.; Zhu, Q.; Wei, Y.; Xu, B., Achieving Stable and Fast Potassium Storage of Sb₂S₃@ Mxene Anode Via Interfacial Bonding and Electrolyte Chemistry. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2023**, *451*, 138891 %@ 1385-8947.
44. Li, M.; Huang, F.; Pan, J.; Li, L.; Zhang, Y.; Yao, Q.; Zhou, H.; Deng, J., Amorphous Sb₂S₃ Nanospheres in-Situ Grown on Carbon Nanotubes: Anodes for Nibs and Kibs. *Nanomaterials* **2019**, *9* (9), 1323 %@ 2079-4991.
45. Xiao, B.; Zhang, H.; Sun, Z.; Li, M.; Fan, Y.; Lin, H.; Liu, H.; Jiang, B.; Shen, Y.; Wang, M.-S., Achieving High-Capacity and Long-Life K⁺ Storage Enabled by Constructing Yolk-Shell Sb₂S₃@ N, S-Doped Carbon Nanorod Anodes. *Journal of Energy Chemistry* **2023**, *76*, 547-556 %@ 2095-4956.
46. Li, X.; Liang, H.; Liu, X.; Sun, R.; Qin, Z.; Fan, H.; Zhang, Y., Ion-Exchange Strategy of Cos₂/Sb₂S₃ Hetero-Structured Nanocrystals Encapsulated into 3d Interpenetrating Dual-Carbon Framework for High-Performance Na⁺/K⁺ Batteries. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2021**, *425*, 130657 %@ 1385-8947.
47. Lu, Y.; Chen, J., Robust Self-Supported Anode by Integrating Sb₂S₃ Nanoparticles with S, N-Codoped Graphene to Enhance K-Storage Performance. *Science China Chemistry* **2017**, *60*, 1533-1539 %@ 1674-7291.

48. Nithya, C.; Modigunta, J. K. R.; In, I.; Kim, S.; Gopukumar, S., Bi₂S₃ Nanorods Deposited on Reduced Graphene Oxide for Potassium-Ion Batteries. *ACS Applied Nano Materials* **2023**, *6* (7), 6121-6132 %@ 2574-0970.
49. Lin, J.; Lu, S.; Zhang, Y.; Zeng, L.; Zhang, Y.; Fan, H., Selenide-Doped Bismuth Sulfides (Bi₂S₃-X_{sex}) and Their Hierarchical Heterostructure with Res₂ for Sodium/Potassium-Ion Batteries. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2023**, *645*, 654-662 %@ 0021-9797.
50. Wang, C.; Lu, J.; Tong, H.; Wu, S.; Wang, D.; Liu, B.; Cheng, L.; Lin, Z.; Hu, L.; Wang, H., Structural Engineering of Sulfur-Doped Carbon Encapsulated Bismuth Sulfide Core-Shell Structure for Enhanced Potassium Storage Performance. *Nano Research* **2021**, *14* (10), 3545-3551 %@ 1998-0124.
51. Qin, Y.; Zhang, Y.; Wang, J.; Zhang, J.; Zhai, Y.; Wang, H.; Li, D., Heterogeneous Structured Bi₂S₃/MoS₂@ Nc Nanoclusters: Exploring the Superior Rate Performance in Sodium/Potassium Ion Batteries. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2020**, *12* (38), 42902-42910 %@ 1944-8244.
52. Hsieh, Y.-Y.; Tuan, H.-Y., Architectural Van Der Waals Bi₂S₃/Bi₂Se₃ Topological Heterostructure as a Superior Potassium-Ion Storage Material. *Energy Storage Materials* **2022**, *51*, 789-805 %@ 2405-8297.
53. Sun, X.; Wang, L.; Li, C.; Wang, D.; Sikandar, I.; Man, R.; Tian, F.; Qian, Y.; Xu, L., Dandelion-Like Bi₂S₃/Rgo Hierarchical Microspheres as High-Performance Anodes for Potassium-Ion and Half/Full Sodium-Ion Batteries. *Nano Research* **2021**, 1-8 %@ 1998-0124.
54. Liu, Y.; Li, M.; Zheng, Y.; Lin, H.; Wang, Z.; Xin, W.; Wang, C.; Du, F., Boosting Potassium-Storage Performance Via the Functional Design of a Heterostructured Bi₂S₃@ Rgo Composite. *Nanoscale* **2020**, *12* (48), 24394-24402.
55. Yuan, L.; Zhou, Q.; Li, T.; Wang, Y.; Liu, Z.; Chong, S., Promoting Superior K-Ion Storage of Bi₂S₃ Nanorod Anode Via Graphene Physicochemical Protection and Electrolyte Stabilization Effect. *Applied Energy* **2022**, *322*, 119471 %@ 0306-2619.
56. Wei, Y.; Hou, W.; Zhang, P.; Soomro, R. A.; Xu, B., Bi₂S₃ Nanorods Encapsulated in Iodine-Doped Graphene Frameworks with Enhanced Potassium Storage Properties. *Chinese Chemical Letters* **2022**, *33* (6), 3212-3216 %@ 1001-8417.